

Economic Contribution of the Employees of Silehkhana Department in the Marwar State of Rajputana

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Abstract: *Economic cycle has always been a crucial and dominant factor for the life of any country, state, or nation since the dawn of the civilization, moving ahead in this line we find that Marwar state of Rajputana i.e. modern day Rajasthan has always been in the forefront to give it the present day recognition to Rajasthan in its many shades of society, culture, tradition and many more. And there were many departments and portfolios in those days working primarily to strengthen Marwar as a whole and Silehkhana department or Armoury was one of them so an effort is being made to signify the important role of this department in the economic cycle of Marwar state.*

Keywords: Rajputana, medieval times, Arms, weapons, Marwar state, Silehkhana, Daroga, Departments, Economy.

I. INTRODUCTION

In almost all the empires and states of the medieval world, there is a partial, Minute and short description of the Arms and weapons along with king, people, administration and treasury .In Arthashastra, Chanakya has described the army as one of the seven major organs of the state and asked every king to spend a major portion of the state's income on security, army and weapons manufacturing. In Rajputana the Marwar state's defencesystem depended on the military force of the state, the strength of the administration and the capacity of the armoury.

Marwar state had 36 departments and 5200 record Books(BAHIS) related to them, one of these departments was of Silehkhana which was working as the axis of the state. Here, in the Records of Silehkhana Talke(affair) and Jawahar Khana Talke(affair), we find mention of the manufacturing, maintenance, repair, expenditure on weapons, the names of the weapon smiths along with the caste system of the workers and the expenditure on various items related to Silehkhana. . But there has been a lack of efforts to study these details on a large scale.

These Silehkhana records help us to get an idea of the defence system of Marwar state, the various departments established to maintain the military system and the officials of those departments and their caste system, to explain this idea more clearly. For some other departments of Marwar stateA brief description has been given of those who appear to be directly and indirectly related to the Sileh Khana department.From these records we also get the details of the caste system of the workers, how the workers of jinagar community were responsible for covering the sword sheath and sewing it, the workers of Suthar(carpenter) caste were responsible for arranging good quality wood for the sword sheath, the blacksmith were The workers who used to make and repair swords.

Further, it is also interesting to know that a single weapon, which came into existence for defence and security, attained its physical form by touching the zenith of the skills of uncountable numbers of workers and continued to express within itself the natural talent and dedication of the workers for years.

While working on this topic many questions emerged in the mind, answers to some questions have been found and further study and research work will have to be done to find answers to some questions. Such as -

How apart from the king, soldiers of different branches of the army along with various officials and workers played their role in the economy of the state?

In this cycle of economy, how different castes and families provided their services for generations, and how the state provided them employment and services and how the state played its economic role by providing them employment.

How the Silehkhana department emerged as an industrial unit of the state in the Marwar and how the state got new industries and new sources of income.

From the Recordson Marwar history, we come to know that during the rule of Maharaja Vijay Singh Ji, Bheem Singh Ji, Man Singh Ji, Takht Singh Ji and Maharaja Jaswant Singh Ji, there seems to be an increase in the manufacturing and import of weapons.

From the sources we get information about offensive and defensive weapons. In V.S.1801(1744A. D.)Under lethal weapons, 1995 numbers of Arms includingswordswith different names like Dhoop (Khanda), Katti ,Taraju, Teg (Jodhpur) were kept in Silehkhana, other kind of weapons like Gupti, Khanjar, Katar, jamdhar, Battle Axe, Pistol, Spear, Arrow, Bow are prominent and the defensive Equipmentswhich were used to protect the body like shieldswere also kept in the Silehkhana department of Marwar state.

In the SilehkhanaDepartment, the work of making, storing and repairing weapons was done and along with all these functions The main work of the Silehkhana Department was to decide the price of newly manufactured weapons and to keep records of various weapons and to keep an account of the expenditure incurred in the manufacture and repair of weapons.

From the sources we come to know that during the reign of Maharaja Jaswant Singh, Mahesh Kachwaha was the head of Silehkhana department, who was also present in the battle of Dharmat andgave his life in the battle.After that, there is a description of the appointment of khinchi Sundar Das, khinchiNar singh and during the time of Maharaja Vijay Singh, there is information about the appointment of Gehlot Vijeraj, during the time of Maharaja man singh ji, there is a description of the appointment of Gehlot Bhagwan Das .

How much was spent on offensive and defensive weapons, it is still difficult to ascertain in the context of Marwar on the basis of the data that has come to my notice, that is why as my research work progresses, I will discuss more about this subject. After studying, I will try to present the final results and figures, just like the V.S. of Jaipur state. In 1789 Rs. It is known that Rs. 17802-8-0 will be spent on weapons and V.S. In 1989 Rs. Spent 1926-2-6 and V.S. 1780-8-0 were spent in 1815.

Some other departments and officials of the Marwar state which were directly or indirectly related to the functioning of the Silehkhana department and influenced the economy, were as followed :

- Sileposa Department - The main officer of this department was called Daroga.Only the armed warriors were called as Silepos and as per the orders of the state, when appointed at different places, these armed warriors would serve with their weapons with full awareness. Silopos were accompanied by their Daroga during military campaigns.

For example, in the battle of Gangarada (1754) fought by the combined forces of Jayapa Maratha and Ramsinghji of Amer against Marwar Maharaja Vijay Singh ji, when Vijay Singh ji was defeated and went towards Nagaur, the forces of Jayapa Maratha and Ramsingh surrounded the Nagaur fort. When he started causing physical harm to the people delivering supplies, than the daroga of silepos department Saidas Chauhan, along with Khokhar Kesar Khan and a Gehlot warrior, succeeded in killing Jayapa by pretending to be a mutual fight.

1. Musharaf of Sileposa: Arrangements for special expenditure on the weapons of armed warriors were made by the Musharaf of the Silepos department. From V.S. 1824 to V.S.1884 There is description of appointment to 16 inspectors ,In which Joshi Balu was appointed to this post for 5 times.
2. Khase khajanaDaroga :person appointed on this post was the chief officer of the treasury. This was a kind of banking system where coins of different metals were collected and the currency was withdrawn as and when required. This department was the main source of expenditure on the Silehkhana department. In this department, various branches of Brahmins (Shrimali, Tiwari, Ojha, Vohra, Chhangani, Purohit) etc. were appointed to the post of Inspector.
3. Jarjarkhana Department : This department was created for the manufacturing of gold and silver jewellery for the state.The head officer of this department was also called inspector. Here, the work like making gold bars, silver on weapons like swords etc. was done by the workers from goldsmith community. In this department mainly people of Brahmin community were taken into consideration for appointment to the post of daroga

4. Jhuharkhana Department: This was the Jewellery and gem department that used to assist in doing the work of setting gems on jewellery on arms and weapons. Among the Brahmanas, mainly Vyas Brahman were appointed as inspectors or Daroga. After Sawai Ram Vyas, this post became hereditary.

Apart from these departments and officials, officials like Bakshi, Chowki Navesh, Topkhana Inspector, Topkhana Musharraf, Marwar Mint Inspector, Killi Khana Inspector, Lead Mine Inspector etc. and their related departments partially influenced the Silehkhana department in the economy of Marwar.

For example, Bakshi in Bikaner state got an annual income ranging from Rs. 4000 to Rs 5000 and Piyad Bakshi is mentioned getting a salary of Rs 38 and 10 annas per month. And a gunner in the artillery department gets an annual salary of Rs. 150 to Rs. 210.

The philanthropic works done by the state can also be briefly shown among the other sources of obtaining money in the money flow of the economic cycle of Marwar state. Some examples can also be presented in the context of Marwar which are directly related to the war-time situation, for example

- There is a description of financial assistance provided by the state for the treatment of injured soldiers during and after the war, under which financial assistance was provided to the injured under Pattabandhai (Dressing) and Jakhmana.
- The criteria for compensation was decided according to the status or post obtained in the state and compensation or financial assistance was given according to the affected body part. Normally this rate is Rs 5 for every ambush/injury was fixed.
- To commemorate the bravery, the Rajput rulers honoured their chieftains and Pattayats (Patta holders) by giving them villages, for example, Jagat Singh Udavat was given a village of Rs 500 rekh
- When soldiers become martyred in the battle there was a provision to give jobs to their sons on vacant posts and financial assistance was given to widows under Mali Imdaad, in Amer state it was called Jeevika, in Marwar it was called Takseer and in Kota it was called Paltu. For example, the widow of a Jamadar was given a pension of Rs 2 per year, who was martyred in the battle of Lambiya while against the Deccan soldiers.
- Daulat ram Silepos's widow was provided financial assistance of Rs 7 and 11 annas and 6 paise (7-11-6). In Marwar, this assistance and grant was given according to the number of dependents present in the family.

After knowing the usefulness of various officials and departments in the economic system of Marwar state, we get brief information about the income and economic condition of the artisans (Rojindars and Mahindars) working in Silehkhana, under which the salary was given to Rojindars on regular basis and Mahindars on monthly basis. Rewards, loans etc given by the state are in some or the other forms became an integral part of the economy of Marwar; whose details are available in known records.

- We get information from the records of Silehkhana that the repairing work of swords and daggers was done by the artisans of the blacksmith community like Pitha, Pira, Bhita, Hathi, Rama, Kushal, Jeevan etc. and they used to get 2 taka from the state.
- The repairing of the shields was to be done in the month of Vaisakha (11 month of Hindu calendar) by blacksmith Panna, Pira, Seervi Seva, Jat Kesia, potter Wagha, who were getting 2 taka per day as remuneration/wages from the state treasury.
- Siklighar (Moyal) community used to do repair weapons while staying in the fort, for this work the artisans named Kanha, Lachha, Magha, Chutra, Kisna, Shiva etc. got wages on daily basis of 1 taka per day.
- Regarding cleaning the weapons of Silehkhana department, 3 yards of white cloth was purchased from blacksmith Kisaniya for Rs. 1 and 3 annas. Blacksmith Pira repaired English guns and was given Rs 2 for the purchase of parts. The sword hilt was purchased from blacksmith Nathu which cost Rs 5. and 1 Aana. 2 sword hilts from blacksmith Mudhawas purchased which cost Rs 7 and 1 aana. 13 English spears were purchased from blacksmith Natha for which Rs 19 and 2 taka were given.
- Sikli Ghar Lohar who used to forge weapons in the fort. They were paid a daily wage of 1 taka per day. We get information from Silehkhana records that weapons were purchased from blacksmith Surjabhan in which 10 small knives of moon shape were priced at Rs 1 each and 14 ordinary knives were priced at Rs 1 each. Is included.

- 8 spears were purchased from blacksmith Natha, Rs 15 per spear was paid accordingly.
- For making 12 sword hilts, Mochi udiya was given, Rs 1 and 2 annas from the state treasury
- When the cobbler Kushaliya, resident of Ahmed Nagar, came to Jodhpur and gifted the Maharaja with his knife, then on behalf of the state, he was given the honour of balabandhi 1 in quantity (Burhanpur) along with moliya 1 in quantity (worth 1.25 annas).
- Hind skins (Sambhar) was purchased from cobbler Ratna at a cost of Rs 32 for 112 pieces. Names of some women are also mentioned, such as the name of Mochan- Sivaji's daughter-in-law, Mochan- Rupa's daughter-in-law, Uda's daughter-in-law, Luba's daughter-in-law are present in preparing the Rakia of the sword, and they were given 1 taka per day from the state. .
- On the purchase of 1 sword and 1 shield from Joshi Sahdev, he received a royalty of Rs 3 vijeshahi.
- Rs 1 Given to Dabgar Rupala for repairing one piece of shield.
- The cobblers working in Mayanagar (sheath house) used to get 1 taka daily.

Sometimes even people belonging to different weapon making castes used to gift the Maharaja a weapon, for example, Mistry Babu showed Maharaja Saaheb Takht Singh Ji a Chandravat (Moon shape) knife whose handle was made of ivory.

Blacksmith Rama, who was from Didwana, gifted a Khando and Katari to Maharaja Saaheb, then the Maharaja increased his honour by graciously giving him Moliya, 1 Balabandi, 1 Burhanpur.

Among the workers of the goldsmith caste, goldsmith Isardas and goldsmith Tulsidas were the best artisans of their time. They were an excellent artisan in gold plating on the sword's handle, hilt. Goldsmith Raichand, who was the goldsmith of Sirohi, also served the Marwarroyal family. Goldsmith Nanak was expert at applying gold bars to weapons.

In this way, despite the lack of presence of economic resources at one place, an effort has been made about the active participation and contribution of the officials and workers related to the Silehkhana department of Marwar in the economy of Marwar and further work will be done on this work in detail.

II. CONCLUSION

Every department played crucial role in the economic cycle of any institution so does the Silehkhana department of Marwar state in the medieval times which was a very important and key factor source of economy and safety, security of the king, people and state as the whole. Further it helps us to understand that how it was a source of creating employment to many people in the state also.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Vikram Singh; Jodhpur Silehkhana Astra Shastrarivigat; Rajasthanis hodh sansthan and Mehrangarh museum trust jodhpur. (2015).
- [2]. Vikram Singh; Jodhpur Rajyaka Astra Shastra; Maharaja Man Singh Pushtak Prakash Shodh Kendra Durg Jodhpur. (2013).
- [3]. Hukam Singh; Marwarkeohadedarokaitihaasmeinyogdan; Maharaja man Singh Pushtak Prakash Shodh Kendra durg Jodhpur. (2013).
- [4]. Saxena R. K. ; The army of the rajputs ; Sarojprakashan Udaipur; 1989